

Practice abstract 01

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 www.polirural.eu

PoliRural: Future Oriented Collaborative Policy Development for Rural Areas and People - an introduction

Changes in rural areas, such as depopulation, land abandonment and the loss of biodiversity, may proceed very slowly yet are often irreversible. Policymakers can steer these developments in order to reduce their negative impacts but this requires knowing whether current policy instruments are effective, who is benefiting from them and in what measure, what driving forces will be most influential and how they will affect people, planet, profits and land-use. To be truly useful, this knowledge must transcend siloed thinking and be the corollary of a joint effort uniting different actors under a common cause.

PoliRural will provide this knowledge by combining several key activities needed to design effective place-based, human-centric and forward-looking rural policies. These include actionable research that takes place within an inclusive learning environment where rural populations, researchers and policymakers come together to address common problems; an evaluation exercise that uses text mining to assess the perceived effectiveness of past or planned policy interventions; and a foresight study that tries to glean the development trajectory of agriculture and its allied sectors until 2040 using several scenarios in which the evolution of rural populations occupies a central place. As a result of these activities, PoliRural will leave decision makers at different levels of government better equipped to tackle existing and emerging rural challenges, rural populations more empowered and rural areas more resilient.

This project has received funding from European Union's Horizon H2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 818496.

Practice abstract 02

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PoliRural's Innovation Hub

PoliRural intends to transform rural policy, avoiding the pitfalls of old practices and advancing new knowledge fit for the post-2020 society. To contribute to this, PoliRural is designing a multi-governance policy Innovation Hub that makes all regional stakeholders active participants, fostering cross-sharing of knowledge and building a strong enabling stakeholder community for the rural ecosystem.

The aim of the Polirural Innovation Hub is to offer a public user interface and introduction to the innovations of the project. It will be a central and virtual space, where all stakeholders (policymakers, public servant, regional development agencies, NGO, citizens, scientists, developers, data experts, planners) will meet and share their needs and achievements to improve policy and decision making on local, regional and eventually national level. The core of the Innovation Hub will be the Digital Innovation Hub platform, which will support the sharing of information with other projects and initiatives.

To this end, the Polirural Digital Innovation Hub will provide four distinctive sections, or spaces, that cater for both internal and external users:

- An interaction space with forums, dialogue and Wiki capabilities to support stakeholder interaction;
- A learning space for Massive Open Online Courses to facilitate dissemination and uptake of knowledge and methodology developed through the project;
- An experimentation space for testing analytics and visualization including text mining and system dynamics based on real data;
- A development and hosting space for creating virtual instances of the shared reference to be used by each pilot when developing their applications.

